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POLICY BRIEF

LEVERAGING EU BIODIVERSITY POLICY TOWARDS NET POSITIVE IMPACTS ON GLOBAL BIODIVERSITY

Funded by
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BACKGROUND

Human wellbeing and planetary health critically depend on biodiversity and related contributions of nature to people. Current global and national efforts to maintain and restore biodiversity remain insufficient to halt, let alone reverse the dramatic ongoing processes of species extinction in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems¹. The Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) calls for transformative change worldwide to address the interconnected crises of biodiversity loss².

Climate change as well as current geopolitical tensions add to the challenge of preserving biodiversity globally^{3,4}. Climate change modifies the conditions of habitat quality at a pace that surpasses the adaptive capacity of an increasing number of ecosystems⁵. This adds to the uncertainty involved in coordinating global conservation efforts, because we still know too little about how ecosystems systemically respond to biodiversity decline⁶. Geopolitical tensions and conflicts tend to reinforce major drivers of biodiversity loss, resulting in additional security risks as in a vicious circle⁷. For example, wars and violent conflicts disrupt global supply chains leading to costly and often pollution intensive

national adaptation measures³. Moreover, trade barriers imposed by major players in the global trade system, such as the US and China, are likely to accelerate land cover change in some of the world's most biodiverse tropical landscapes⁸. At the same time, conflicts linked to climate change and the use of biodiverse natural resources, such as forests, or their destruction through forest fires, are on the rise⁹. Importantly, geopolitical tensions tend to change policy priorities away from addressing biodiversity loss.

Delaying action to bend the curve of global biodiversity decline is costly compared to the benefits of acting now¹⁰. As a major global player, the European Union (EU) must maintain and raise awareness that prosperity in its member countries depends crucially on functioning ecosystem globally. The EU must therefore pursue ambitious biodiversity policy targets including via its economic, agri-environmental, and trade policies. Here we propose ingredients of a science-based strategy to coherently align and strengthen EU sectoral policies towards conserving and restoring biodiversity within and outside its borders.

HOW TO MAINTAIN AND RESTORE BIODIVERSITY INSIDE THE EU

The implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy is advancing, but massive progress is needed to reach the 2030 targets¹². Europe's biodiversity, habitats, and species are still under threat mostly because of unsustainable agriculture and forestry practices, urbanization, climate change, modification of water regimes, pollution, illegal hunting and invasiveness of alien species. To reverse the current trend and speed up recovery, as aimed for in the EU Biodiversity Strategy, these causes of biodiversity loss must be seriously addressed. This includes research to improve the evidence base on how biodiversity contributes to wealth and sustainable development in the region.

Biodiversity has been included in major EU policy frameworks, but with limited results. For example, the EU Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), since 1985, and the Strategic Environmental Assessment Directives (SEA, since 2001) list biodiversity as one of the key themes upon which significant negative impacts must be assessed and mitigated. And yet, biodiversity conservation is too often being traded off against other sectoral policy goals, including the expansion of renewable energy¹³ or tourism development in biodiversity-rich coastal ecosystems¹⁴. At the same time, promising regulatory initiatives, such as the Restoration law and the European Green Deal are

gradually being weakened as political priorities shift, not at least in response to mounting geopolitical tensions¹⁵.

Short-term perspectives in policy planning, the persistent sectoral fragmentation of policy design and implementation, and failures of state regulatory policies in the face of market forces still represent major obstacles for biodiversity to be ranked higher on the policy priority list. Correspondingly, siloing of disciplinary knowledge and the corresponding polarization of views, structures and practices often impede the development of systemic solutions to govern complex human-environment interactions. For example, when sectoral policies refer to biodiversity they often do so independently and thus miss out on opportunities to integrate priorities and related actions. On the other hand, biodiversity is systematically seen as a limiting factor in sectoral development initiatives. Examples of (missing) policy links that require attention are summarized in Box 1.

Many of the policies mentioned in Box 1 could remain inconsequential or even become counterproductive for biodiversity if not coherently aligned. Spatial planning can be used as an inclusive and integrative planning tool to increase coherence across sectoral policy instruments and coordinate governance for biodiversity conservation and restoration.

TOWARD NET-POSITIVE IMPACTS ON GLOBAL BIODIVERSITY

In addition to declining biodiversity in the EU, research shows that the EU drives environmental pressures far beyond its borders—particularly in tropical regions with high conservation value—through trade^{16,17} and finance¹⁸ flows. EU imports are a major driver of deforestation, forest degradation, and the overharvesting of wild populations globally, through demand for food and fiber^{19,20}, illegal wildlife trade²¹, and harmful fishery subsidies²².

In recent years, the EU has advanced several legislative initiatives aimed at reducing its global biodiversity footprint. Recognizing the role of biodiversity loss “embedded” in EU imports—the increasing pressures on natural ecosystems occurring in producer countries driven by EU consumption—the *EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030* mandates the inclusion of biodiversity provisions in all Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) and stricter assessments of their impacts on ecosystems. The EU has also adopted the landmark *EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR)*, which requires that select forest-risk commodities placed on the EU market are deforestation-free.

While this represents a major step forward, critical analyses highlight gaps in scope and implementation that undercut impacts. Assessments of the EUDR (see Box 2) highlight the risks for leakage and the need to expand scope, ensure effective enforcement, and support strong partnerships with producer countries for the legislation to have an effect on deforestation. And while nine of eighteen FTAs signed by the EU since 2011 contain a Biological Diversity

clause—and most also include ecosystem-specific clauses for forest and fish products—these provisions often lack specificity or enforcement mechanisms, meaning they are unlikely to mitigate the pressures increased trade put on ecosystems²². For instance, all of these FTAs exclude biodiversity conflicts from the general dispute settlement mechanism. The financial sector also remains insufficiently regulated in terms of biodiversity impacts, despite a growing consensus that finance must play a stronger role, both in redirecting harmful subsidies and in ensuring that EU investments support nature-positive outcomes.

Importantly, while cleaning up the EU’s own footprint is a key first step for a coherent global EU biodiversity strategy, it is insufficient for two main reasons. First, causal pathways between EU consumption and impacts are largely indirect, i.e. global trade flows will flexibly maneuver around restrictions and shift footprints to other consumer markets as long as total resource demand is not reduced. Second, harm avoidance is not enough. Especially when other global actors are withdrawing from collective environmental action, the EU can take a leading role in forging partnerships around biodiversity conservation, not the least in the Global South. This can be done through direct support to spatially targeted biodiversity-protecting actions, from protected areas to payments for environmental services systems. Such efforts can also reduce backlash from producer countries against EU sustainable supply-chain and trade policies and should remain high on the EU’s agenda.

BOX 1 & 2: POLICY GAPS AND RISKS

BOX 1: EXAMPLES OF EXISTING AND MISSING POLICY LINKS CONCERNING BIODIVERSITY

A key statement in the BDS2030 is that biodiversity considerations need to be better integrated into public and business decision making at all levels. We checked across different policy instruments, in particular between Common Agriculture Policy (CAP), Farm to Fork (F2F), Territorial Agenda 2030 (TA2030) and Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (BDS2030).

For example, “Restore degraded ecosystems and reverse the loss of biodiversity” is required by BD2030, F2F and CAP. The same instruments are aligned on the need for member states to elaborate and evaluate National CAP Strategic Plans (BDS2030, F2F and CAP). The TA2030, however, remains silent on the fact that both policies target the same territory.

Moreover, the TA2030 refers to the “Habitats Directive and the need for Rural Development Policy”, a policy that can be found also in the CAP and the

BDS2030, but not in the F2F – a missed opportunity to mainstream biodiversity as a cross-cutting issue.

Similarly, the BDS2030 explicitly mentions the need for “improved governance and inclusive approaches”, which is addressed as “joint approach” in the F2F, but not reflected in the CAP or the TA2030.

Finally, the BD2030 and the TA2030 are consistent in promoting “Network(s) of protected areas, nature-based solutions and blue and green infrastructures”. And yet, the CAP and the F2F instead call for establishing “agri-environmental schemes to maintain seminatural features on farmland”, while the TA2030 is the only policy framework including a measure for “sustainable soil and land use for sustainable livelihoods” that none of the other frameworks refer to.

BOX 2: THE EU DEFORESTATION REGULATION

The EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) requires placing cattle, cocoa, coffee, natural rubber, palm oil, soy, and timber products on the EU markets to implement due diligence systems that allows for tracing the products back to their places of origin and ensuring they were not produced on recently deforested land. While representing an important step-up in the EU’s work against deforestation, concerns have also been raised that the effect of the regulation simply risks being a segregation of global supply-chains, with EU markets becoming a niche for deforestation-free products²³. Research has also stressed the importance of member-state enforcement in reducing risks for laundering of non-compliant produce²⁴, as well as risks of unintended effects when EUDR provisions do not align with pre-existing, sometimes environmentally more demanding national policies and value-chain governance mechanisms in producer countries (e.g., for soy in Brazil)²⁵.

It is important to recognize that while the EU is a major importer of deforestation embodied in international trade, because forest loss is in many places predominantly driven by domestic demand, EU consumption of the commodities covered by the EUDR accounts for only around three percent of global agriculture-driven deforestation²⁶. The largest potential impact of the EUDR therefore lies in potential positive spillovers, in terms of consumer-goods companies adopting EUDR provisions also for non-EU markets, producer countries adopting and enforcing domestic forest conservation policies, and other consumer countries following suit. Compared to the aim of just cleaning up EU supply-chains, this requires more attention to forging more supportive and inclusive partnerships with farmers, producer countries, and other consumers.

POLICY RECOMMEN DATIONS

To strengthen the breadth of biodiversity policy and lead a paradigm shift into biodiversity-positive inhouse and globally, the EU must address three key policy gaps:

BROADEN CROSS-SECTORAL ACTION AND POLICIES TERRITORIALIZATION

In the EU: Nature and biodiversity must be mainstreamed across sectoral policies and territorialized with spatial planning. Foster the role of spatial planning as the backbone of policy mixes. Improve the generation of biodiversity data and knowledge relevant for spatial planning and strengthen the role of spatial planning to enable cross-sector spatial negotiations, in particular through co-creating and co-exploring scenarios of change²⁷. Spatial planning should guide restoration investments into those areas where improvements are most urgently needed or where cost-efficient implementation is possible.

Globally: Recognize the importance to protect also non-forest ecosystems, by expanding the scope of the EU trade and biodiversity policy regime—e.g., FTA ecosystem clauses and the EUDR—to also cover these. Introduce mandatory biodiversity risk disclosure and screening in financial regulations. Look also beyond trade and finance to work with countries in the Global South to protect valuable biodiversity more directly.

INCREASE POLICY COHERENCE:

In the EU: Promote an integrated alignment and coherence of sectoral policies to enhance the value of biodiversity. To navigate conflicts arising from vested interests in sectors like agriculture, urban development, energy, and infrastructure, spatial planning is a promising governance tool to enable alignment of policies across sectors. The inclusion and assessment of biodiversity impacts must become a standard component of biodiversity-positive planning in all policy domains. The focus stands on ensuring that agricultural, economic, and infrastructure policies do not offset the effectiveness of biodiversity conservation policies, instead they contribute to enhanced biodiversity sectoral policies and actions. More genuinely targeted “biodiversity first” actions are

required, rather than just making it a cross-cutting concern of doing no harm in business-as-usual development practices.

Outside the EU: Ensure consistency across policy areas, by shifting from seeing biodiversity considerations as add-ons in trade and finance policy, giving it equal weight to other policy objectives. This includes (1) avoiding provisions in the EU-Mercosur FTA to seriously undermine the implementation of the EUDR and (2) safeguards against EU-external effects of domestic measures to maintain and restore biodiversity. A coherent and ambitious policy mix is essential to align the EU’s global role with its biodiversity commitments and to ensure a just and sustainable transition for all.

CO-DESIGN & PARTNERSHIPS:

Early and transparent stakeholder engagement should be embedded in policy planning beyond the environmental sector. Participatory governance empowers stakeholders through co-creation and shared learning, fostering collective responsibility and fairer distribution of benefits and burdens.

Develop equitable partnerships with producer countries to support sustainable land-use transitions, ensuring mutual benefits and capacity-building. Prioritize trade partners where EU demand accounts for a large share of the export market and drives substantial losses in biodiversity (countries like Brazil, Côte d’Ivoire, Honduras, and Papua New Guinea)²⁸.

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THE HORIZON EUROPE CLUSTER TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE FOR BIODIVERSITY

The Horizon Europe Cluster on Transformative Change for Biodiversity is a strategic initiative within the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. It aims to address the root causes of biodiversity loss through systemic, societal transformation, focusing on integrating biodiversity considerations into various sectors by promoting fundamental changes in economic, social, and governance structures. The cluster supports interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research projects that explore innovative pathways for halting and reversing biodiversity decline, emphasising the need for inclusive, equity-driven approaches. This collective effort supports the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and contributes to the broader global agenda for transformative change in biodiversity conservation.

Launched in October 2021, the cluster has since fostered collaboration among multiple projects to maximise impact and

facilitate knowledge sharing. The cluster originally included 11 Horizon Europe-funded projects, and it is now expanding with new projects funded by the European Commission on the same topics. These projects collectively work towards developing actionable knowledge and tools to implement transformative changes across Europe and beyond.

For more information, you can visit the official Horizon Europe Cluster 6 page: [Cluster 6: Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment](#).

The 11 projects that jointly organized the “Mainstreaming Biodiversity in Policy Making” conference were: CLEVER, BioValue, RAINFOREST, BAMBOO, Bedrock, BioNext, BIOTraCes, TRANSPATH, BioAgora, Planet4B and DAISY. Below are short descriptions of all.

CLEVER

Website: clever-project.eu

The CLEVER project identifies new leverage points for sustainable transformation by quantifying biodiversity and other impacts of trade in major raw and processed non-food biomass value chains. This will be the result of studying the links between international trade in agricultural and forest products and biodiversity. The regional foci of CLEVER lie in EU trade with South America (soybean and beef in Brazil) and Central Africa (forest products in Cameroon and Gabon). The final goal is to address

governance solutions for more sustainable production and consumption, influencing decision-making, in collaboration with stakeholders from politics, the private sector and civil society. With several members long engaged in science-policy interface, the consortium will leverage CLEVER knowledge and tools to strengthen international panels and enhance science-industry cooperation for sustainable bioeconomic transformation.

BIOVALUE

Website: biovalue-horizon.eu

The BioValue project focuses on leveraging transformative change to enhance the value of biodiversity in spatial planning processes. It employs a research framework built on three key perspectives: spatial planning, environmental assessment, and economic and financing instruments. This framework is being tested through three case

studies, known as “Arenas for Transformation”: Rewetting Peatlands and reforestation in Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, Germany; Municipal spatial planning in Mafra, Portugal; and Urban planning in Trento, Italy. By driving systemic changes in spatial policymaking, BioValue supports the integration of biodiversity into EU strategic actions.

RAINFOREST

Website: rainforest-horizon.eu

The RAINFOREST project contributes to enabling, upscaling and accelerating transformative change to reduce biodiversity impacts of major food and biomass value chains. Together with stakeholders, they co-develop and evaluate just and viable transformative change pathways and interventions, by identifying stakeholder preferences for a range of policy and technology-based solutions, as well as governance enablers, for more sustainable food and biomass value chains. The project then evaluates these pathways and solutions using a novel combination of integrated assessment modelling, input-output modelling and life cycle

assessment, based on case studies in various stages of the nexus, at different spatial scales and organizational levels. This coproduction approach enables the identification and evaluation of just and viable transformative change leverage points, levers and their impacts for conserving biodiversity (SDGs 12, 14-15) that minimize trade-offs with targets related to climate (SDG13) and socioeconomic developments (SDGs 1-3). The project elucidates leverage points, impacts, and obstacles for transformative change and provides concrete and actionable recommendations for transformative change for consumers, producers, investors, and policymakers.

TRANSPATH

Website: transpath.eu

Biodiversity is declining at unprecedented rates, which will lead to significant consequences at a global scale. There is widespread agreement among science and policy communities that conventional policies will not be enough to halt biodiversity loss or curb climate change. More urgent and ambitious ‘transformative changes’ are needed in the ways in which we live, and the ways in which our economies and societies use and relate to nature and natural resources. Transformative change focuses on the fundamental system-wide restructuring of the root causes to sustainability challenges, which are underpinned by complex social paradigms, values and behaviours. TRANSPATH sets out diverse mechanisms to support and enable the addressing of these issues by: 1) drawing on diverse contexts in Eastern and Western Europe, Africa and Latin America, to engage

with those who affect and are affected by trade regimes and associated ‘greening’ mechanisms; 2) designing policy packages and other interventions to enable the emergence of leverage points at different scales of action in ways that change the choice architecture underlying daily decisions; 3) considering the synergies and trade-offs of actions across multiple people and places, and the role of incentives and political barriers to implementation; 4) delivering a suite of Transformative Pathways with a Toolbox of Transformative Interventions for triggering and enabling these pathways; and 5) guiding practitioners on how to enable and navigate pathways through a Transformative Navigation Toolkit, acknowledging that arriving at what constitutes a ‘transformative pathway’ is also a product of an iterative and adaptive process that emerges and evolves over time.

BAMBOO

Website: bamboo-horizon.eu

Biodiversity faces a severe risk of a sixth mass extinction, and global trade networks allow consumption in one region to drive biodiversity loss in another, yet current tools for assessing these impacts remain limited. In BAMBOO, we address this gap by focusing on non-food biomass and developing models that quantify biodiversity impacts using species richness, mean species abundance, functional diversity and ecosystem services, updating LC-IMPACT and GLOBIO and adding new impact categories for terrestrial, freshwater and marine systems. We create a hybrid multiregional input-output (MRIO) model that merges EXIOBASE and FABIO, link it to our impact assessment methods and the integrated assessment model IMAGE, and

use it to analyse global trade and identify leverage points for halting and reversing biodiversity loss under present and future scenarios. We test our models in two case studies—fishmeal production in Peru and cotton production in Tanzania—and develop an online tool to make them accessible to stakeholders, while also releasing all models openly on Zenodo. Overall, BAMBOO provides detailed insights into how biomass trade affects biodiversity and ecosystem services and improves the ability to identify leverage points, thereby supporting better environmental decisions, science-based targets and the SDGs.

BEDROCK

Website: bedrock-project.earth

Our food systems are major drivers of global change and urgently need a sustainability transition, yet despite widespread commitments from companies, financial institutions and governments to make supply chains for commodities like palm oil, soy, beef and cocoa more sustainable and free from tropical deforestation, progress remains poor and unsustainable practices persist. Because tropical deforestation drives climate change, biodiversity loss and the degradation of ecosystem services vital to millions of people, this project develops and applies a systems-level evaluation framework to assess how effective current supply-chain policies—ranging from

private-sector pledges to mandatory due-diligence requirements—are in reducing deforestation and which combinations of policies work best while minimizing unintended consequences. We build a conceptual and analytical framework that accounts for multiple perspectives, trade-offs, context, spillovers and equity concerns, and apply it to key deforestation frontiers. Four interconnected work packages integrate stakeholder insights, theories of change, data and analytical methods to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions across major deforestation-linked supply chains, including soy, beef, cocoa and palm oil.

BIOAGORA

Website: bioagora.eu

BioAgora is a European collaborative project funded by the Horizon Europe programme. It aims to connect research results on biodiversity to the needs of decision-making in a targeted dialogue between scientists, other knowledge holders and policy actors. Its main outcome will be the development of a fair and functional Science Service for Biodiversity that will orchestrate processes and initiatives at the Science-Policy Interface at the European level. To achieve its objective, BioAgora partners 1) develop the Science Service for Biodiversity's governance structure and systems model by testing it in real life and iteratively improving it over the project's duration resulting in a fully functional service; 2) design knowledge exchange

networks across EU Member States that ratchet up the implementation of biodiversity commitments as planned in the EU's Biodiversity Strategy for 2030; 3) analyse the existing landscape of Science-Policy Interfaces, assess their policy tools and the current biodiversity knowledge held in Europe; 4) provide tailored pathways on how to better orchestrate science-policy interactions to support the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030; 5) provide capacity-building to empower the EU's multidisciplinary research community and diverse group of other knowledge holders and users in bringing transformative change for biodiversity; and 6) engage with a broad range of actors such as policymakers, scientists, businesses, and citizens.

BIONEXT

Website: bionext-project.eu

BIONEXT is a research and innovation project that joins the fight for nature and biodiversity. The project produces new evidence to better understand biodiversity loss and demonstrates how biodiversity underpins every aspect of life; the water we drink, the food we eat, and our health. To secure

and protect these values, the project demands transformative change: BIONEXT's goal is a sustainable society, where links between biodiversity, water, food, energy, transport, climate, and health are acknowledged and nature and biodiversity are a part of everyday choices and policymaking.

BIOTRACES

Website: biotraces.eu

There is growing recognition that even the full implementation of current conservation and restoration efforts is not enough to reverse the alarming trend of biodiversity loss. Alongside this, the urgent need to halt the ongoing destruction and exploitation of nature has never been clearer. What we need is a transformative change. This is defined as the "fundamental, system-wide reorganisation across technological, economic, and social factors, including paradigms, goals and values" (IPBES 2019). The BioTraCes project is designed to spark this transformative change by adopting an action research approach. This

approach empowers initiatives to address the root causes of biodiversity loss. What is more, it promotes equity and justice for both people and the planet. Our researchers develop knowledge, tools and novel approaches towards a society in harmony with nature. This helps to boost biodiversity across Europe. We aim at tackling public policies, local and corporate strategies to be more inclusive and just. Thus, BIOTraCes is in line with the European Green Deal and the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations.

PLANET4B

Website: <https://planet4b.eu/>

The PLANET4B project, launched in 2022 to understand what shapes biodiversity-related decisions at individual, community, and institutional levels, has significantly advanced this understanding through three years of research, network building, and policy engagement. The consortium explored how biodiversity appears in scientific, business, and public communication; examined links between intersectionality, behaviour theories, and biodiversity; and developed a Transdisciplinary Research Framework to assess these issues. It compiled and tested 100 creative methods—such as photo voice, night hikes, and

community filmmaking—to influence how people relate to biodiversity, gathering them into an accessible Catalogue. Through case studies with Learning Communities and multi-stakeholder Advisory Boards, the project investigated sectors and initiatives with strong biodiversity impacts and identified potential leverage points, presented through Transformative Change Stories. It also produced policy recommendations, training materials, business and civil-society guidelines, and an open knowledge hub, alongside extensive research outputs now freely available.

DAISY

Website: https://soziologie.uni-halle.de/professuren/ilkhom_soliev/3508610/3508610_3563133/
<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101181857>

DAISY (DigitAI, technological and Social innovation mixes enabling transformation for biodiversity and equity) aims to understand how interventions (innovations, regulations, financial incentives and tools affecting social norms and emotions) and their mixes can drive systemic change and transformation for biodiversity and equity, offering concrete policy recommendations. For this, DAISY 1) Investigates processes supporting current innovations and identifies emerging ones in key domains of agri-food, energy, education and urban and regional development; 2) Develops, tests and provides intervention mixes for transformative change across practical, political and personal spheres, and 3) Engages and enhances the response-ability of civil society, policymakers,

and businesses to implement and amplify transformative action. To achieve these goals, DAISY analyses social, economic, and political processes, maps existing innovations, assesses their transformative potential, and develops, tests and assesses interventions to be taken up by policies to address biodiversity loss and equity. DAISY conducts case studies (spanning from using digital apps through commons governance to degrowth models), workshops, and (social science) experiments, working collaboratively with a range of participants. The project will provide recommendations to decision-makers and build capacity among stakeholders. Additionally, it will foster collaboration with key networks and across a range of domains to amplify its impact.ù

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